

Spectrophotometric Studies on Vanadium(V), Niobium(V) and Tantalum(V) Complexes with Violuric Acid

R. M. AWADALLAH

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Aswan, Assiut University, A.R. Egypt

Manuscript received 16 March 1979, accepted 30 December 1979

Spectrophotometric measurements in the ultraviolet region within the range 200-250 nm is performed to study the reaction of violuric acid with vanadium(V⁵⁺), niobium (Nb⁵⁺) and tantalum (Ta⁵⁺). The results obtained verified that V⁵⁺, Nb⁵⁺, and Ta⁵⁺ form chelate compounds with measurable absorbance at $\lambda=208, 212$ and 217 nm in buffer solutions of pH 9.5, 9 and 9, for V⁵⁺, Nb⁵⁺ and Ta⁵⁺ violurate solutions, respectively. The stoichiometry and the stability constants of the complexes were determined from the spectrophotometric data.

In the present work, the formation of complex compounds between violuric acid and V⁵⁺, Nb⁵⁺ and Ta⁵⁺ ions as the spectrophotometric measurements indicate, are reported and discussed.

VIOLURIC acid is of great use as a good organic complexing reagent for the formation of metal-chelate compounds and a metal indicator for the analytical (volumetric and gravimetric) determination of minute amounts of transition metals.

Violuric acid was introduced as an indicator for the complexometric titration of copper with complexon(III)¹. Violuric acid was also used for the gravimetric microdetermination of palladium² and for the photometric determination of copper³. Niobium (V) and tantalum (V) were determined spectrophotometrically using oxine⁴, alizarin red S and quinizarin-3-sulphonic acid⁵.

Experimental

Solutions :

Standard solutions ($5 \times 10^{-3}M$) of either V⁵⁺, Nb⁵⁺, or Ta⁵⁺ were prepared by dissolving the appropriate amount of V₂O₅ (A.R., 99.9%) in hot HCl (A.R.), few mls of HNO₃ (A. R.), then completing the solution to the requisite volume using bidistilled water, and fusing the A.R. Nb₂O₅ and Ta₂O₅ (99.9%) with K₂S₂O₇ and dissolving the cake in 20% tartaric acid⁶.

$1 \times 10^{-2}M$ -Violuric acid solution was prepared by dissolving the accurately weighed portion of the reagent in redistilled water.

Oxalic, boric, succinic acids, Na₂SO₄, Na₂B₄O₇·10H₂O and Na₂CO₃ buffers of pH 1.5-11 were prepared according to Thiel, Schulz and Coch⁷ and standardised using Pye Unicam Model 290, 2 pH Meter.

Working Procedure :

The spectrophotometric measurements in the ultraviolet region were recorded on the Pye Unicam SP 8000, Ultraviolet Recording Spectrophotometer with matched silica cells, 1 cm light path. The working solution was prepared by mixing the metal ion with ligand-buffer mixture, using blank solution containing the same concentration of violuric acid as in the case of the test solutions of V⁵⁺, Nb⁵⁺ and Ta⁵⁺, violuric acid to compensate the effect of absorbance due to ligand.

Results and Discussion

On mixing V⁵⁺, Nb⁵⁺ or Ta⁵⁺ solution with violuric acid a pale rosy colour is developed due to the formation of complex compounds.

Spectrophotometric Measurements :

The spectrograms of V⁵⁺, Nb⁵⁺ and Ta⁵⁺ violurate complexes are characterised by one apparent maximum peak. The spectral absorbance of the chelates is affected by some factors which are discussed briefly in the followings :

i) Effect of pH ;

$1 \times 10^{-5}M$ solutions of either V⁵⁺, Nb⁵⁺ or Ta⁵⁺ and $4 \times 10^{-5}M$ -violuric acid were used for studying the influence of pH on the complex formation. The spectral absorbance of the solutions increases with the increase of pH reaching maximum at pH 9.5 in case of V⁵⁺ violurate ($\lambda_{max} = 222$ nm) and 9 in case of Nb⁵⁺ ($\lambda_{max} = 212$ nm) and Ta⁵⁺ violurate ($\lambda_{max} = 215$ nm) complexes then slows down. At the

same time the absorption bands shift to a higher wavelength as the pH increases. This may be due to the generation or progressive formation of different interconvertible species.

The increase of absorbance may be attributed to the probable and gradual increase of complex formation whereas the decrease of absorbance beyond the maxima may be due to the effect of higher alkalinity of buffer solution which may cause a dissociation (or hydrolysis) to the complexes formed or form another sort of complexes.

ii) *Effect of Violuric Acid Concentration :*

On keeping the metal ion concentration invariable at $5 \times 10^{-6}M - V^{5+}$, $1 \times 10^{-4}M - Nb^{5+}$ and $5 \times 10^{-6}M - Ta^{5+}$, whereas that of violuric acid is changed from $8 \times 10^{-7}M - 5 \times 10^{-5}M$ in the case of V^{5+} -V.A. solutions, $6 \times 10^{-5}M - 6 \times 10^{-4}M$ in case of Nb^{5+} -V.A. solutions and $1 \times 10^{-6}M - 5 \times 10^{-5}M$ in case of Ta^{5+} -V.A. solutions, the spectral absorbance increases gradually with the increase of ligand concentration, then tends to approach a limiting value in case of V^{5+} and Ta^{5+} due to saturation attainment. Maximum absorption band does not alter in case of Nb^{5+} , whereas in case of V^{5+} -V.A., λ_{max} shifts to $\lambda = 205$ nm (hypsochromic shift) and λ_{max} in case of Ta^{5+} -V.A. shifts to 204 nm (hypsochromic shift) with the increase of violuric acid concentration.

(iii) *Effect of Metal Ion Concentration :*

On keeping the violuric acid concentration constant at $2 \times 10^{-5}M$, whereas that of V^{5+} was changed from $5 \times 10^{-8}M$ to $5 \times 10^{-7}M$, that of Nb^{5+} was varied from $5 \times 10^{-6}M - 3 \times 10^{-4}M$ and that of Ta^{5+} was changed from $1 \times 10^{-6}M$ to $4 \times 10^{-5}M$, the spectral absorbance of V^{5+} , Nb^{5+} and Ta^{5+} violurate complexes increases with the increase of metal ion concentrations. λ_{max} shifts to 208 nm in case of V^{5+} -V.A., 218 nm in case of Nb^{5+} -V.A., and 217 nm in case of Ta^{5+} -V.A. complexes, at higher metal ion concentration, while at lower concentrations, λ_{max} appears at $\lambda = 205, 228$ and 215 nm in case of V^{5+} -V.A., Nb^{5+} -V.A. and Ta^{5+} -V.A. complexes, respectively.

Beer's law is valid for applying violuric acid as analytical reagent for the microdetermination of the elements. The lowest amounts that can be detected and determined are 5.1 ppm, 7.4 ppm and 1.8 ppm with extinction modulus $3.6 \times 10^7, 2.5 \times 10^4$ and 3.7×10^5 for V, Nb and Ta (as metals), while the highest amounts are 101.9 ppm, 37.2 ppm and 7.2 ppm having extinction coefficient values equal to $7.9 \times 10^8, 2.95 \times 10^4$ and 2.7×10^6 for V, Nb and Ta (as metals), respectively. The higher values of extinction coefficient make the method easier to be applied for the determination of microamounts of the metals.

Stoichiometry of the complexes :

The stoichiometric ratios of the complexes were determined under optimum conditions favouring maximum colour development. The methods applied for the determination of the stoichiometry (composition) of the chelates are the molar ratio (M.R.), straight line (S.L.), continuous variation (C.V.), slope ratio (S.R.), and limiting logarithmic (L.L.). The results obtained are recorded in Table 1. These results reveal the formation of 2:1, 1:1, 1:2, 1:3 and 1:4 complexes.

TABLE 1—STOICHIOMETRIC COMPOSITION OF V^{5+} , Nb^{5+} AND Ta^{5+} VIOLURATE COMPLEXES

Method	V^{5+} chelates	Nb^{5+} chelates	Ta^{5+} chelates
M.R.	2:1, 1:1, 1:2 1:4	1:1, 1:2, 1:3	2:1, 1:1, 1:2 1:3
C.V.	2:1, 1:1, 1:2	2:1, 1:1, 1:2 ; 1:3, 1:4	2:1, 1:1, 1:2 1:3, 1:4
S.L.	1:1, 1:2, 1:4	1:1, 1:3, 1:4	1:2, 1:3
S.R.	1:1, 1:2	1:4	1:1
L.L.	1:1, 1:3	1:3	1:4

M.R. = molar ratio, C.V. = continuous variation,
S.L. = straight line, S.R. = slope ratio,
L.L. = limiting logarithmic.

The Apparent Formation Constant :

The values of the apparent formation (stability) constants of the chelates established in solution were evaluated from the results of the spectrophotometric methods, namely, the molar ratio, continuous variation, straight line and limiting logarithmic methods, are reported in Table 2. The equation

TABLE 2—VALUES OF FORMATION CONSTANTS OF V^{5+} , Nb^{5+} AND Ta^{5+} VIOLURATE COMPLEXES

Method	Ratio	Kf of metal chelate of		
		V^{5+}	Nb^{5+}	Ta^{5+}
M.R.	1:1	3.582×10^9	0.197×10^9	3.621×10^{10}
	1:2	1.942×10^{14}	1.657×10^{14}	2.686×10^{16}
	1:3		4.356×10^{19}	1.2997×10^{24}
	1:4	4.485×10^{27}		
C.V.	1:1	0.275×10^9	0.744×10^9	0.144×10^9
	1:2	5.971×10^{14}	2.314×10^{14}	
	1:3			0.835×10^{21}
	1:4		0.267×10^{26}	
S.L.	1:1	0.748×10^8	0.020×10^8	
	1:2	9.21×10^{14}		0.255×10^{16}
	1:3		0.803×10^{19}	0.297×10^{23}
	1:4	8.483×10^{29}	0.085×10^{26}	
L.L.	1:1	2.58×10^8		
	1:2			
	1:3	1.712×10^{25}	0.347×10^{23}	
	1:4			2.976×10^{29}

utilised for the determination of K_f by molar ratio and continuous variation methods has the form :

$$K_f = \frac{(A/Am)}{[1 - (A/Am)]^{(n+1)} \cdot n^2 [L]^n}$$

where :

K_f = apparent formation constant,
 A = absorbance at a given ligand concentration, L ,

A_m = limiting absorbance,
 n = stoichiometric ratio (number of ligand groups in the chelate molecule).

For the straight line method, β_n can be determined from the relation :

$\beta_n = \log ([M^{n+}] \cdot [L]) / (\log A - \log V)$ in which
 V = volume of the mixed solution.

From the results of the limiting logarithmic method, β_n and hence, K_f can be calculated by using the equation :

$$\log \beta_n = \log (A/\epsilon_n) - (m \log [M^{n+}] + n \log [L])$$

where :

ϵ_n = molar extinction coefficient of the complex with the stoichiometric ratio (ligand/metal ion) = n .

The chelation between violuric acid and V^{5+} Nb^{5+} and Ta^{5+} can be typified as follows :

References

1. P. P. SOLODOVNIKOV, *Zh. Ahalit. Khim.*, 1963, **18**, 1026.
2. M. ZIEGLER and O. GLEMSE, *Mikrochim. Acta*, 1956, 1515.
3. M. ZIEGLER, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1958, **164**, 387.
4. I. M. ISSA, R. M. ISSA and R. M. AWADALLAH, *Egypt. J. Chem.*, 1975, **18**, 215.
5. I. M. ISSA, R. M. ISSA and R. M. AWADALLAH, *Egypt. J. Chem.*, 1975, **18**, 221.
6. N. H. FURMAN, "Standard Methods of Chemical Analysis", D. Van Nostrand Company, Inc., Princeton, New Jersey, Toronto, New York, London, Vol. 1-The Elements, Sixth Edition 1966.
7. H. T. S. BRITTON, "Hydrogen Ions", D. VAN Nostrand Company, Inc., 4th Edition, Vol. 1, 1956.